

Behaviour of Thiosalicylamide at Dropping Mercury Electrode

A. BASU and S. C. SHOME

Chemical Laboratories, Presidency College, Calcutta

Manuscript received 30 June 1977, revised 22 February 1978, accepted 3 March 1978

Polarographic behaviour of thiosalicylamide has been investigated at a dropping mercury electrode with the variation of pH, mercury pressure, temperature, concentration of thiosalicylamide and the maximum suppressors. The electrolytic products of thiosalicylamide have been isolated and the mechanisms of the electrode reactions have been suggested. The diffusion coefficient of thiosalicylamide has been determined in 0.50 M KCl at 25° and found to be 3.452×10^{-6} cm² sec⁻¹. The temperature coefficient of the diffusion current at pH=7.48 is 1.64% deg⁻¹ at 25°. In a well buffered (McIlvaine) solution the diffusion current is observed to be directly proportional to $(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ and the concentration of depolariser. Thus, the conditions for a rapid and precise method for the determination of thiosalicylamide down to the concentration of 0.01 mM solution have been established.

SHOME and coworkers^{1,2} first introduced thiosalicylamide as an analytical reagent for metals.

Recently some investigations on the use of thiosalicylamide as an amperometric reagent were carried out in the same laboratory³. In order to determine thiosalicylamide polarographically, its behaviour at d.m.e. is studied in detail and the conditions for 'analytical waves' are laid down.

In organic polarography, few compounds involving reductions of >C=S bond have been studied. Sartori and Furlani⁴ investigated reductions of thiobenzophenone polarographically. It was Lund⁵, who first examined polarographic behaviour of a thioamide i.e. thiobenzamide. Ortho substitution of thiobenzamide by a hydroxyl group is of interest from the stand point of electroreduction. Unlike some derivatives of thiourea⁶, which are not polarographically reducible but yield anodic waves at d.m.e., thiosalicylamide produces different cathodic and anodic waves at d.m.e. with the change of acidity.

Experimental

The polarograms are recorded with Radelkis pen recording polarograph (type OH 101/1), voltmeter being calibrated by OSAW slide wire potentiometer. Micro-electrolysis are carried out using Toshniwal manual polarograph and the spectra are taken by Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, PMQ II type. The pH values are measured by Cambridge pH meter (Bench Model).

An external S. C. E. serves as a reference electrode, connected to the cell by means of agar-KCl bridge except for the case of drawing anodic polarograms in strong acid medium, where S. C. E. is connected by means of a double agar-KNO₃ bridge. The capillary characteristics are measured in 0.5 M KCl solution at -1.10 volt (vs S. C. E.) at a mercury height of 53.00 cms and the value of $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ is $1.367 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ Sec}^{-1/2}$.

Thiosalicylamide is prepared and purified by the usual procedure. An aqueous solution of thiosalicylamide (0.005 M) is prepared as a stock solution. The other reagents are of A. R. quality and their solutions are made in conductivity water.

A McIlvaine buffer solution consisting of disodium hydrogen phosphate and citric acid is used for pH 3-8 and for 8-12, the composition of buffer is disodium hydrogen phosphate and caustic soda. In strong acid solution, HCl and in strong alkaline solution, NaOH are used. For drawing anodic waves in strong acid medium, H₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ are used for maintaining acidity and for supporting electrolyte respectively. Polarograms are recorded at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.50M$) by KCl at 25°, so that the corresponding IR drops are negligibly small and hence neglected. Necessary corrections are made for residual current in the evaluation of diffusion current. Dissolved air is removed by bubbling pure hydrogen gas through the solution and the hydrogen atmosphere is maintained during electrolysis.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH on wave characteristics

The wave characteristics of thiosalicylamide are highly dependant on pH of the solutions. Below pH 4.50, a single well defined cathodic wave is formed. Pronounced maxima are obtained when cathodic polarograms are drawn for thiosalicylamide at a pH within 3.00. The irregularity is eliminated when freshly prepared gelatin solution (0.005%-0.01%) is used as a maximum suppressor. Several other maximum suppressors are found suitable, of which the effects of Triton X100 solution (0.005%-0.001%), methyl red solution (0.005%) are studied. A single well defined cathodic wave is obtained at low pH, whereas a double wave is found within pH 4.50-7.40, of which the first wave decreases with the increase of pH and that of second wave increases with the increase of pH (Fig. 1).

In order to explain the electrode reaction, prolong electrolysis of thiosalicylamide is carried out in 0.1N H₂SO₄ medium at dropping mercury electrode (at +0.2 volt vs S.C.E.). The U. V. spectra of the electrolysed solution is taken and the maximum absorbance is found to be at 355 nm. This clearly indicates the formation of the complex of mercury and thiosalicylamide^{1,2}. Since mercury (II) and thiosalicylamide form a complex in acid medium in the ratio of 1:4, the equation for the anodic wave at d.m.e. and the anodic reactions can be written as follows :-

The equation of wave at d.m.e. at 25°C is

$$E_{dme} = E^\circ_{\text{Hg}^{2+}} + \frac{0.0591}{2} \log \frac{i}{(i_a - i)^4} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

On plotting E_{dme} (vs S.C.E.) against log $\frac{i}{(i_a - i)^4}$, a straight line is obtained, the slope of which is found to be 0.0316, showing Hg has been oxidised to Hg²⁺ ion.

Effect of concentration of thiosalicylamide :

Table 2 shows the diffusion current i_d of different polarograms of solutions containing 1.00mM to 0.01mM thiosalicylamide per liter at a constant ionic strength of 0.50M. The i_d values are calculated from the wave heights of respective polarograms making due correction for the residual current. The diffusion current constant $I_d \left(= \frac{i_d}{C_m t^{1/2}} \right)$ and the diffusion coefficient D of thiosalicylamide have been calculated for μ=0.50M, Temp. 25°.

TABLE 2—DIFFUSION CURRENTS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THIOSALICYLAMIDE.

C (mM)	Temp. = 25°, μ = 0.50 M				Alkali (0.1 N NaOH) Anodic i _a (μA)	Acid (0.1 N H ₂ SO ₄) Anodic i _a (μA)
	pH = 3.10 Cathodic	i _d (μA)	I _d	D × 10 ⁶ Cm ² Sec ⁻¹		
0.010	0.062	4.536	3.491			
0.050	0.310	4.536	3.491	-0.160		
0.100	0.600	4.390	3.271	-0.296		
0.250	1.610	4.711	3.765	-0.782	-0.610	
0.350	2.170	4.537	3.491	-1.060	-0.800	
0.500	3.060	4.477	3.401	-1.540	-1.150	
0.750	4.500	4.389	3.270	-2.360	-1.720	
1.000	6.150	4.500	3.436	-3.310	-2.440	

Constancy of I_d and D within experimental limit indicates the proportionality of the diffusion current with the concentration of thiosalicylamide, and it offers a method for the polarographic determination of thiosalicylamide. The height of the anodic wave in alkaline medium shows a limiting value with increasing concentration beyond 1.00M which may be due to adsorption of HgS precipitate over the dropping mercury electrode.

From the equation of anodic wave in acid medium, one can expect the shift of E_{1/2} (Vs S.C.E.) with the change of concentration of thiosalicylamide.

Thus,

$$\text{When } i = i_d^3/2, \quad E_{dme} = E_{1/2}$$

∴ From equation (2) at 25°

$$E_{1/2} = E^\circ_{\text{Hg}^{2+}} + \frac{0.0591}{2} \log \left(\frac{2}{i_d} \right)^3 \dots \dots (3)$$

$$= E^\circ_{\text{Hg}^{2+}} + \frac{0.0591 \times 3}{2} \log 2 - \frac{0.0591 \times 3}{2} \log i_d \dots (4)$$

$$= E^\circ - 0.0885 \log i_d \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

E_{1/2} (Vs S.C.E.) when plotted against log i_d, a straight line is obtained the slope of which is calculated to be -0.0821, while the expected value is -0.0885. Thus, for every ten fold increase in the concentration of thiosalicylamide, the E_{1/2} (Vs S.C.E.) of the anodic wave in acid medium changes by 0.0821 volt (Vs S.C.E.) towards the more negative direction.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the financial assistance to AB. They also extend their gratitude to Dr. D. Banerjee, Ghosh Professor of Chemistry, Calcutta University for helpful discussion.

References

1. S. C. SHOME and M. MAZUMDER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 46, 155.
2. K. SUR and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 48, 145.
3. S. C. SHOME, M. MAZUMDER and A. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1976, 53, 1140.
4. G. SARTORI and G. FURLANI, (UnOV. Trieste, Italy) *Ann. Chim. (Rom)* 1954, 44, 95-112, C. A. 1954, 48, 13470 b.
5. H. LUND, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.* 1960, 25, 3313.
6. P. ZUMAN, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.* 1955, 20, 646.
7. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1953, 75, 2484.
8. L. MEITES, *Polarographic Techniques*, Interscience Publishers, Inc. New York, 1955, p-25.
9. K. KINDLER, *Ann*, 1923, 187, 431.
10. K. KINDLER, *Arch. Pharm.* 1926, 389, 265.
11. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, *Polarography*. Vol-II Interscience Publishers, Inc. New York 1952, p-681.
12. K. SUR, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1970, p-162.
13. M. MAZUMDAR and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*. 1971, 56, 149.